

QUIZ

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COURSE CODE : ACA-401D

PERIOD NUMBER: 6

INSTRUCTOR: GULMA

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author used Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 10)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. One of the following is not considered plagiarism

- Falsifying data
- Using the exact words of a source without a quotation marks or indentation
- Borrowing all or part of another student's paper or having somebody else write your paper or parts of the paper
- Using another writer's words/ideas with proper citation¹**

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, ed. Wayne C. Booth et al., 8th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 51, 208; EUCLID, *ACA-401D Coursepack Period 1*, 2015, 9–10, 45, <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/>.

2. **One of the following is not part of the key points for paraphrasing**
- The paraphrased words must be your own words
 - The writing style to express the author's idea must be different from the style the author used
 - Accurate representation of the information you are providing
 - The language can resemble to the word of the author²**
3. **A research question conducted to answer what we must understand before we know what to do is called**
- Conceptual question
 - Practical question
 - Applied question³**
 - Theoretical question
4. **Which of the following graphic forms is used to show trends and deemphasize specific values?**
- Bar chart
 - Histogram
 - Line graph⁴**
 - Scatter plot

² EUCLID, *ACA-401D Coursepack Period 1*, (Washington DC: Euclid University Press, 2015), 24.

³ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 17.

⁴ Turabian, 66.

5. **Which of the following sentence is not correct about bibliography and author-date styles?**

- In bibliography style, signal by placing a superscript number at the end of the sentence
- In author-date style, signal by placing a parenthetical citation next to your reference to it.
- In author-date style, reference lists are printed at the bottom of each page (footnotes).⁵**
- In bibliography style, notes are printed at the bottom of each page (footnotes) or in a list collected at the end of your paper or the end of each chapter.

6. **One of the following issues is not related to the practical feasibility and doability of a research problem.**

- Possibility of access to potential sites and potential research population
- Availability of source of information, and availability of time and resource to collect and analyze data
- Availability of literature about the research problem⁶**
- Researcher's knowledge and skills

⁵ Turabian, 86–87.

⁶ Linda Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End* (California: Sage Publications, 2008), 32.

7. **Which of the following is correct about introduction to the study in developing a proposal?**

- Identifies what is already known about your topic/problem
- Sets the stage for explaining and justifying the research⁷**
- Includes methods for data collection and analysis, and rationale for the methods used
- Involves the projected timetable for your research

8. **Which of the following terms are used to evaluate the trustworthiness of a qualitative research?**

- Credibility, reliability and validity
- Credibility, dependability, and transferability⁸**
- Credibility, reliability, and generalizability
- Reliability, validity, and transferability

9. **Which of the following is true about advantages of house style?**

- Ensure consistency in the document
- Contribute to a corporate image of “one ORGANIZATION”
- Streamlines and increases the efficiency of the writing and editing process
- All are advantages of house styles.⁹**

⁷ Bloomberg and Volpe, 44–45.

⁸ Bloomberg and Volpe, 99–100.

⁹ World Health Organization, *WHO Style Guide* (Malta: WHO Graphics, 2004), 5.

10. **Based on WHO style guide which of the following is applied**

- The references within a bibliography might not necessarily presented alphabetically, according to the names of the authors.
- Use of initial capital letters for words might not be limited and consistent throughout a publication
- Chemical names should follow the International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry (IUPAC) rules¹⁰**
- Use of contractions in WHO information products is possible

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. California: Sage Publications, 2008.

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¹⁰ World Health Organization, 9–10.